

FATIGUE GROWTH OF MATRIX CRACKS IN 0/90/0 GFRP AND CFRP LAMINATES

L. Boniface and S. L. Ogin
Department of Materials Science and Engineering
University of Surrey, Guildford, UK

ABSTRACT

The growth of individual transverse ply cracks during tension-tension fatigue of 0/90/0 GFRP and CFRP laminates has been observed using transmitted light and penetrant-enhanced X-radiography, respectively. The crack growth rate in both types of laminate is independent of crack length but depends on the spacing between cracks. A model for matrix cracking based on the stress intensity factor for a growing transverse ply crack is applied to the experimental observations and crack growth rates are described using a Paris relation.

INTRODUCTION

Multiple transverse ply cracking occurs in cross-ply composite laminates under both static and fatigue loading and may lead to a long-term degradation in laminate properties such as stiffness. Various authors have described the development of transverse cracks and attempted to model the associated stiffness changes using different approaches.

The growth of transverse ply cracks in a transparent GFRP 0/90/0 laminate under static loading was described in early work by Bailey and co-workers [1-4]. They observed that cracks initiated at the edge of the laminate and increased in density with increasing stress, reaching a saturation crack density approximately equivalent to the transverse ply thickness.

A similar pattern of transverse cracks develops under fatigue loading [5,6] and has been termed the "characteristic damage state" by Reifsnider and co-workers who suggest that this is characteristic of a particular laminate configuration and is independent of load history and environment.

Several authors have used fracture mechanics approaches for modelling the growth of matrix cracks [7-13]. Ogin et al [14-16] proposed a model for crack growth based on the stress intensity factor, K , at the tip of a growing transverse ply crack which is assumed to be flat and to span the thickness of the ply. The approximate expression for the stress intensity factor is

$$K = \sigma_t \sqrt{2d} \quad (1)$$

where σ_t is the stress in the transverse ply acting on the crack and $2d$ is the transverse ply thickness. (The stress, σ_t , includes mechanical and thermal contributions, both modified by a shear-lag term). Growth of the crack across the width of the ply is governed by the stress intensity factor, which is independent of crack length but depends on the crack spacing (through σ_t) and on the transverse ply thickness.

This model has previously been applied to predict stiffness reduction during fatigue of a commercial (0/90)_s GFRP laminate at different stress levels [15,16] and to fatigue crack growth in 0/90/0 GFRP laminates [17]. In the present work, the model has been applied to experimental observations of crack growth under fatigue loading of CFRP and transparent GFRP laminates with different transverse ply thicknesses at different peak stresses and R ratios.

EXPERIMENTAL

Transparent cross-ply GFRP laminates were fabricated from E-glass fibres in 'Epikote' 828 epoxy resin and CFRP laminates were autoclave moulded from XAS/914 prepreg. The fibre volume fraction in both types of laminate was approximately 60%. Load-controlled tension-tension fatigue tests were carried out on 20mm wide parallel-sided coupons at different peak cyclic stresses and R ratios. Fatigue testing conditions and laminate configurations are summarised in the Table 1.

Table 1 Laminate configurations and fatigue testing conditions

laminate	CFRP (0/90 ₃) _s	CFRP (0/90 ₂) _s	GFRP (0/90) _s	GFRP (0/90) _s
90° ply	0,5mm	0,75mm	0,52mm	0,78mm
peak stress (MPa)	150 285	235 360 500	95 140 170	90
R	0,01	0,1	0,1, 0,5	0,1
frequency(Hz)	10	10	5	5

The development of transverse cracks was monitored at intervals throughout the tests from photographs of the transparent GFRP coupons and radiographs of the CFRP coupons made using a zinc iodide radio-opaque penetrant. The length of individual cracks and the longitudinal spacing between a crack tip and its nearest neighbour were measured from the photographs. In-situ optical microscopy during fatigue loading was used for detailed examination of crack morphology in GFRP coupons.

RESULTS

The development of the transverse ply crack pattern in all of the laminates depended on the mode of loading and, under fatigue loading, on the maximum cyclic stress [17]. Under static loading and fatigue loading at high maximum stress, cracks initiated at the edge of the coupon and grew by fast fracture across the complete width of the transverse ply. At low maximum cyclic stress and at high cyclic stress when the crack spacing was small, cracks grew slowly across the width of the ply.

Slow crack growth at peak fatigue stresses just below the static transverse ply cracking stress is illustrated in Figures 1a and 2a for GFRP and CFRP coupons respectively. Cracks initiated at the edge and grew slowly across the width of the coupon over periods of thousands of cycles. At cyclic stresses above the static cracking threshold, cracks grew slowly only when the average crack density had increased so that the crack spacing had fallen to about 2-3 times the transverse ply thickness [17].

Measurements from individual transverse cracks showed that the growth rate depended on crack spacing and was independent of crack length, in contrast, for example, to the growth of a through-thickness crack in an isotropic plate. This dependence of growth rate on crack spacing is demonstrated by plotting crack length (normalised with respect to the coupon width) against number of cycles (Figures 1b and 2b) for the individual cracks indicated in Figures 1a and 2a. The current crack spacing is indicated on the figures. In Figure 1 for the GFRP coupon, crack A grew at an approximately constant rate across the full width of the coupon with a constant spacing. The growth rate of crack B decreased as the spacing decreased until growth was arrested by close overlap with an adjacent crack, reducing the spacing to 0.25mm, i.e. approximately half the transverse ply thickness. In Figure 2 for a CFRP (0/90₃)_s coupon, crack A grows with a constant spacing at a constant rate and cracks B and C overlap each other, significantly reducing their spacings and consequently reducing their growth rates. The data

for individual cracks in each test showed a trend of increasing crack growth rate with increasing crack spacing (Figure 3) above about one half to one transverse ply thickness, depending on the stress level.

The crack growth rate was affected by changes in the crack tip morphology as well as by interaction between cracks, which may partly explain the large amount of scatter in growth rates at a given spacing indicated in Figure 3. Branching of the crack tip sometimes occurred (probably due to local irregularities in fibre distribution) and there was a corresponding decrease in the growth rate of both branches until part of the divided crack tip was able to grow beyond the branching point [17]. Some cracks initiated at the edge of the coupon and were arrested (at a length equivalent to 1-2 ply thicknesses) for a number of cycles before continuing to grow across the width of the ply. Microscopical observations showed that during this 'incubation period', the crack grew slowly to span the ply thickness along the complete length of the crack. (The significant increase in the rate of growth across the width of the ply after this period corresponded to the crack attaining the flat, full-thickness profile to which the expression for K applies [14]).

For each test, average crack growth rates corresponding to a range of crack spacings were found from measurements on the individual cracks. The growth rate of individual transverse cracks could then be described by a Paris fatigue crack growth relationship of the form $da/dN=f(\Delta K, K_{MAX})$ where da/dN is the crack growth rate, ΔK is the stress intensity range, K_{MAX} is the maximum stress intensity and A and m are constants. The average crack growth rate is plotted against the stress intensity factor range calculated from equation 1 in Figures 4 and 5 for the GFRP and CFRP laminates respectively. Previous work [17] has shown that although the scatter is large, the complete set of data for the GFRP and CFRP laminates is described by a function of ΔK more closely than K_{MAX} , i. e. $da/dN=A\Delta K^m$.

DISCUSSION

The crack growth rate measurements described here are in agreement with earlier experimental observations on the growth of individual cracks in GFRP and CFRP laminates [14,17] and have been analysed using a model outlined here and developed in earlier work [14,16], which predicts a dependence of crack growth rate on crack spacing but not on crack length. The observation of crack length independence for the growth of matrix cracks across the ply width is also in agreement with the strain energy release rate based models of Hahn and co-workers [7,13] and Dvorak and Laws [12]. In the present model, the effect of interaction between neighbouring cracks is quantified using a shear lag expression which gives the peak stress in the transverse ply between two cracks. A more complete analysis of crack interactions may require taking into account the changing geometry of the growing crack tip which is observed, for example, during edge-crack incubation and crack branching. These changes in crack tip morphology lead to variations in the stress intensity factor and therefore affect the crack growth rate.

CONCLUSIONS

Observations of the fatigue growth of transverse ply ply cracks indicate that growth rate is independent of crack length. The growth rate is affected by interactions between overlapping cracks and changes in the crack tip geometry, both of which change the stress intensity factor at the growing crack tip. A Paris fatigue crack growth relationship of the form $da/dN=A\Delta K^m$ describes the crack growth data in the GFRP and CFRP laminates to within an order of magnitude for different transverse ply thicknesses and R ratios.

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FIGURES

Figure 1(a) Photographs showing slow crack growth at a peak fatigue stress just below the static transverse cracking stress in a GFRP laminate.

Figure 1(b) Crack length (normalised with respect to the coupon width) vs number of cycles for individual cracks indicated in the GFRP coupon in Figure 1a. The crack spacing is also indicated.

Figure 2(a) X-radiographs showing slow crack growth at a peak fatigue stress just below the static transverse cracking stress in a CFRP laminate.

Figure 2(b) Crack length (normalised with respect to the coupon width) vs number of cycles for individual cracks indicated in the CFRP coupon in Figure 2a. The crack spacing is also indicated.

Figure 3 Crack growth rate vs crack spacing for individual cracks in GFRP laminate (transverse ply thickness 0.52mm) at $\sigma_{MAX}=140\text{MPa}$, $R=0.1$.
 ○ growth rate for individual cracks
 ■ average growth rate

Figure 4 Average crack growth rate vs ΔK for GFRP laminates:

- (0/90)_{S1}, transverse ply 0.78mm
- * $\sigma_{TENSILE} = 90\text{MPa}$, $R=0.1$
- (0/90)_{S1}, transverse ply 0.52mm
- $\sigma_{TENSILE} = 95\text{MPa}$, $R=0.1$
- $\sigma_{TENSILE} = 140\text{MPa}$, $R=0.1$
- △ $\sigma_{TENSILE} = 170\text{MPa}$, $R=0.1$
- ◇ $\sigma_{TENSILE} = 95\text{MPa}$, $R=0.5$
- ▽ $\sigma_{TENSILE} = 140\text{MPa}$, $R=0.5$
- + $\sigma_{TENSILE} = 170\text{MPa}$, $R=0.5$

Figure 5 Average crack growth rate vs ΔK for CFRP laminates:

- (0/90)_{2S1}, transverse ply 0.5mm
- △ $\sigma_{TENSILE} = 235\text{MPa}$, $R=0.1$
- ◇ $\sigma_{TENSILE} = 360\text{MPa}$, $R=0.1$
- * $\sigma_{TENSILE} = 500\text{MPa}$, $R=0.1$
- (0/90)_{3S1}, transverse ply 0.75mm
- $\sigma_{TENSILE} = 150\text{MPa}$, $R=0.01$
- $\sigma_{TENSILE} = 285\text{MPa}$, $R=0.01$